

RESIDUAL STRENGTH SIMULATIONS OF SANDWICH PANELS AFTER IMPACT

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SUMMARY

The impact behaviour of sandwich panels with different core structures and their residual strength after impact are investigated. The focus in this study is the development and validation of a procedure which allows to simulate the impacts and to perform numerical residual strength simulations with the pre-damaged FE models.

Keywords: Sandwich panel, Residual strength simulations, Low energy impact simulations, Barely visible impact damage, 4-point bending test, Folded core

INTRODUCTION

The residual strength of sandwich panels after impact is of great concern in many areas. Especially for aerospace applications the residual properties after impact are critical design parameters [1]. Previous experimental investigations revealed significant reduction of compression and bending strength even in case of barely visible damage caused by low energy impacts (BVID) [2].

To avoid expensive and time-consuming test programs (impact tests, 4-point bending tests and compression after impact (CAI) tests), numerical simulations may be useful to assess the impact behavior and to estimate residual strength after impact.

A procedure is developed to simulate low velocity impact tests as well as the residual strength tests (e.g. 4-point bending tests) of impacted sandwich structures. The impact simulations are performed using an explicit code. Afterwards the resulting deformations and damages in the face sheets and the core are transferred from the explicit impact simulation to a new model. With this model implicit non-linear static residual strength simulations are performed.

To validate the numerical simulations a test program is performed. The impact tests are realised using a drop tower with a hard impact body. Different impact energies are used to generate different damage mechanisms in the sandwich panels. After the impacts the bending strength is measured in 4-point bending tests. Additional bending tests with undamaged panels are performed.

SPECIMENS

All the tests and simulations for this study are performed on sandwich specimens (or models) with a folded core. During the manufacturing process of this type of core a planar material is folded into a three-dimensional origami-like structure. The cores as well as the sandwich samples are manufactured at the University of Stuttgart, Germany. The cores are produced in a continuous process and have a trapeze-form zig-zag geometry or 3-HAP (Haupt-Achsen-Paar = pair of principal axes) [3], [4]. Aramid fibre paper impregnated with phenolic resin is used as core material. The core has a height of 20 mm and overall density of 137.5 kg/m³. The cores have two distinct in-plane directions designated as L- and W-direction (see Fig. 1,2).

Figure 1: Foldcore specimen [5]

Figure 2: Unit cell geometry

Both face sheets of the sandwich are CFRP laminates. The used composite structure has 16 plies in a quasi-isotropic layup ($[45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ]_{\text{sym}}$). The thickness of the face sheets is 2mm.

The tested samples have a size of 400x91 mm² and 400x98 mm². The folded core exists only in the middle of the sample and has an in-plane size of 91x98 mm². In the remaining space between the face sheets the core is replaced by a homogeneous filler (Fig. 3).

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND TEST PROCEDURE

Subsequent impact and 4-point bending tests are performed as basis for the numerical simulations. To estimate the decrease of the bending strength due to the impact damages 4-point bending tests are also performed with non-impacted panels.

Impact Tests

The impact tests were performed with a drop tower. The impactor has a mass of 1.56 kg and slides along a vertical rail. The impactor head which actually contacts the sample is ball-shaped and is made of steel. The diameter of the head is 1 inch (25.4 mm).

During the experiments the specimens are fixed to a plate made of laminated wood to achieve smooth bearing conditions and to avoid oscillations of higher frequencies. At the corners the investigated plates are fixed by nylon plates to prevent spring-back. The whole back surface of the panels is supported by the laminated wood plate, avoiding displacement of the rear surface.

To measure the reaction force two acceleration sensors are integrated into the impactor head. The analogue recording of the measuring data is accomplished with a sampling rate of 100 kHz. A laser measuring system mounted at the drop tower records the displacement of the impactor. The same system allows to measure the exact impact velocity and thus the exact impact energy.

4-point bending tests

The 4-point bending test is designed to obtain information about the bending strength of a sandwich panel. The test set-up is built to introduce a constant bending moment into the tested area of the sandwich sample. To do this the sample is loaded at four positions. The schematic drawing of the 4-point bending test set-up can be found in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: 4-point bending test set-up

The sandwich core outside the inner load introductions is replaced by a much stiffer filler. This modification prevents shear-induced failure in the outer regions of the samples during the tests. Because of this the needed sample length can be reduced significantly.

The test set-up is designed according to DIN EN 6061 [6]. The force is introduced by four steel cylinders. Rubber pads are placed between the cylinders and the samples to reduce lateral forces. All samples are tested beyond the ultimate load.

EXPEREMENTAL RESULTS

During the test program 10 samples in each principal (L and W) direction are tested. Two samples in each direction are used to perform 4-point bending tests without prior impact loadings. The remaining 16 samples are exposed to impacts of 5, 10, 20 and 40 Joule impact energy. These energies correspond to kinetic energies of an object with the mass of the impactor (1.56 kg) dropped from heights between 33 cm and 2.6 m .

The observed damages after the impact range from nearly invisible (5 Joule) to a clear visible dent with first fibre fractures (20 Joule) to fibre fractures in all plies (40 Joule). However earlier investigations with similar configurations suggest for all tested impact energies a much higher invisible damage extent. The invisible damage area can be a magnitude larger than the visible dent area, especially for very low impact energies [7].

Comparisons between contact forces caused by the different impact energies are shown in Fig. 4. The maximum force levels increase with the impact energy between 5 and 20 Joule. For 40 Joule the force level decreases again. This phenomenon can be explained by the switch of the primary damage process from mostly delaminations and matrix damages to extensive fibre damages.

The corresponding vertical positions of the impactor with respect to the upper surface of the individual samples are shown in Fig. 5. During the 40 Joule impact the impactor penetrates approx. 1/3 of the complete thickness (24 mm) of the sandwich panel.

Figure 4: Contact forces (experimental)

Figure 5: Penetration depth (experimental)

With all impacted and non-impacted samples bending tests are performed. In case of the impacted specimens the damaged face sheets are subjected to compression. In Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 the results are summarized. The initial non-linearity is caused by the compression of the rubber pads between the sample and the test set-up. The linear slope in the force-displacement diagrams (bending stiffness) is very similar for nearly all tests. The decrease in bending strength however is significant. The relative bending strength in comparison to the lowest measured value for non-impacted panels is summarized in table 1.

Figure 6: Force-displacement diagram (4-point bending tests, L-direction)

Figure 7: Force-displacement diagram (4-point bending tests, W-direction)

For all pre-damaged test samples the collapse occurs in the same way. A crack appears on a line with an inclination of 80° to 85° to the loading direction with the impact position in the middle. The crack propagation originates at the damaged centre of the panel and propagates very fast towards the free edges of the sample, causing an instant drop in the applied force. The collapse of the non-damaged panels follows a different process. The compressed upper face sheet delaminates from core and buckles outwards.

Table 1: Relative bending strength

	Tests in L-direction	Tests in W-direction
no impact	100 %	100 %
5 Joule impact	73 % (2 samples)	84 % / 69 % (2 samples)
10 Joule impact	53 % / 48 % (2 samples)	55 % (2 samples)
20 Joule impact	45 % / 35 % (2 samples)	43 % / 42 % (2 samples)
40 Joule impact	35 % / 33 % (2 samples)	40 % (1 sample)

NUMERICAL MODELS

The impact simulations are performed using LS-Dyna. The data resulting from these simulations, especially the residual deformations and damages in the face sheets and the core can be used to establish a "pre-damaged" model for a residual strength simulation. The non-linear static residual strength simulations are performed using Abaqus (see Fig.

8). Additionally comparative simulations are done with an equivalent non damaged model to asses the drop in strength caused by the impact.

Figure 8: The scheme for the 4-point-bending residual strength simulations

Models Used for Dynamic Analysis

The impact simulations are performed with the LS-Dyna commercial solver. All the major dimensions of the model are chosen according to the actual samples tested during the impact experiments.

For the impactor, the face sheets and the core 4-node Belytschko-Lin-Tsay shell elements (uniformly reduced integration, LS-Dyna type 2) are used. Different material models for the different parts of the model are used. The impactor, which is a solid hardened steel ball in comparable experiments, is assumed to be rigid. The density of the rigid impactor shells is adjusted to get an overall mass of the actual impactor of 1,56 kg. For the paper cell walls an elasto-plastic material (type 24) was adopted. The failure criterion for the paper is based on the maximum plastic strain. For the face sheets the LS-Dyna composite material model 54 is used. Unidirectional layers in composite shell structures can be defined with this material model. Additionally according to the Chang-Chang criteria 4 different failure modes can be specified (fibre tensile/compression and matrix tensile/compression failures). As long as none of these criteria is fulfilled the material is assumed to be elastic. The material properties for the

CFRP face sheets were taken from the tensile tests of the face sheet material and the data sheets of the Cytech HTS/977-2 preregs, the face sheets are made of. The supporting is modelled as a rigid wall.

Due to incompatible meshes of the core and the face sheets, these parts of the model are tied to each other by tied contact interfaces. The contact interface between the faces and the core is a so called LS-Dyna type 7 tied interface. This means the contact algorithm translates not only the translational but also the rotational degrees of freedom between the nodes of shell elements of a face sheet and nodes of shell edges of the foldcore.

The impact energy is controlled by the initial vertical velocity of the impactor. The interaction between the impactor and the upper face sheet is controlled by a contact algorithm with the spherical impactor as the master surface and the upper face sheet as the slave surface. Additional contact algorithms prevent the forceless penetration of the core after a possible destruction of the face sheet and the self-penetration of the walls inside the core.

Transfer of Deformations and Damages and the Models Used for Static Analysis

The results of the impact simulations contain a variety of information about the damage that occurred during the computation. The damages in the plies of the composite face sheets are caused by one of the four failure modes (compressive and tensile failure modes of fibres and matrix according to the Chang-Chang criteria). Each of these modes leads to a different degradation of the properties of the affected ply (Table 2).

Table 2: Degradation of properties due failure mode

Failure mode	Degraded properties
Fibre Tensile Failure	All properties
Fibre Compressive Failure	All fibre and shear properties
Matrix Tensile Failure	All matrix and shear properties
Matrix Compressive Failure	All matrix and shear properties

For all elements of the upper face sheet, where in one or more plies the condition for one of the failure modes is satisfied during the LS-Dyna computation, a new element in the Abaqus model is generated. These elements are provided with degraded properties in the affected ply (or plies). For the computations described in this report the affected properties are reduced to a value of 10% of the initial values.

Due to plastic deformations in the core and damages in the core the FE mesh of the model remains distorted after the actual impact loads have subsided. This mesh is used as the initial mesh for the static 4-point bending simulations.

The definition of the material properties in the Abaqus model is otherwise similar to the material properties used for the impact simulations. The paper walls are elasto-plastic. The single plies of the face sheets are able to fail according to the Hashin failure criteria. As during the impact computations the meshes of the sandwich skins are tied to the core wall mesh by a contact algorithm. Additionally the filler material is modelled with standard 8-node brick elements with elastic material behaviour.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The impact simulations show a good agreement in the prediction of the maximum contact load for most of the impact energies (for example see Fig. 9). The prediction of the maximum penetration depth in case of the 20 Joule impact is overestimated by approx. 20%. It is likely that at this critical impact energy, the shift between matrix failures/delaminations and fibre fractures as the dominant failure mode cannot be properly described by the given model yet.

Figure 9: Contact forces (40 J impact)

Figure 10: Penetration depth (40 J impact)

For the other investigated energies the predicted maximum depths are very similar to the measured ones. However the duration of the impact is underestimated for all simulations (for example see Fig. 10).

During the 4-point bending simulation also a good agreement between the simulations and experiments could be achieved regarding the linear force increase and the collapse position (see for example Fig. 11, Fig. 12 and Fig. 13). The initial non-linearity observed during the experiments and caused by the rubber pads, is not described in the simulations.

Figure 11: Force-displacement diagram (4-point bending after a 5 J impact)

Figure 12: Force-displacement diagram (4-point bending after a 40 J impact)

For the impacted panels the predicted collapse force is slightly overestimated in most cases. This seems reasonable due to fact that most of the imperfections in the real samples could not be adopted to the used models.

Figure 13: Ultimate failure due 4-point bending after a 10 J impact (experiment and simulation)

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the performed simulations provides useful results for the investigated sandwich panels. The investigated approach has the potential to be a valuable tool in the design process of new core and skin configurations. The necessary experimental program could be reduced and simplified. Also the influence of local structure of the core regarding the the impact position (for example the differences between an impact above a folding edge of the core and an impact above a gap in the fold core) can be easily investigated.

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References

1. Zenkert, D.: The Handbook of Sandwich Construction. EMAS publishing, 1997
2. Göttner, W.; Klaus, M.; Reimerdes, H.-G.: Bending strength of sandwich panels with different cores after impact. *In proceedings: ECF16 - 16th European Conference of Fracture*, 2006
3. Fischer, S.; Heimbs, S.; Kilchert, S.; Klaus, M.; Cluzel, C.: Sandwich Structures with Folded Core: Manufacturing and Mechanical Behaviour. SAMPE Europe, Paris, 2009
4. Kehrle, R.; Drechsler, K.: Manufacturing of folded core structures for technical applications, SAMPE Europe, Paris, 2004
5. Heimbs, S.; Mehrens, T.; Middendorf, P.; Maier, M.; Schumacher, A.: Numerical Determination of the Nonlinear Effective Mechanical Properties of Folded Core Structures for Aircraft Sandwich Panels, 6th European LS-DYNA Users Conference, Gothenburg, 2007
6. DIN EN 6061: Aerospace series, Fibre reinforced plastics, Test method, Determination of sandwich flexural strength, 4-point bending, Nov. 1995
7. Labeas, G.; Johnson, A; Mines, R.; Klaus, M.; Siviour, C.: The Impact Performance of Sandwich Structures with Innovative Cellular Metal and Folded Composite Cores. SAMPE Europe, Paris, 2009